

SOCIAL COMPETENCES AND EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE OF FUTURE PE TEACHERS

A statutory project of the UPE in Warsaw Ds. 174; subject: Influence of Workshops Making Use of the Video Interaction Training Method and Interpersonal Training on Development of Future PE Teachers' Social Competences and Emotional Intelligence.

Marcin Czechowski, Joanna Femiak, Anna Kuk

Józef Piłsudski's University of Physical Education in Warsaw

Abstract

The aim of the study is to establish the level of social competences and emotional intelligence amongst future P.E. teachers.

The method of diagnostic survey is applied and the Questionnaire of Social Competences (SCQ) and the Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire (INTE) – which is a Polish adaptation of a tool by Nicola S. Schutte et al. – are used in the study. The research was conducted in April and November 2012. The researched were 1st and the 2nd level students of the teaching specialisation of the Faculty of Physical Education, the UPE in Warsaw. Their total number was 156 – 70 women and 86 men aged 20-27.

It was found that the women had a higher level of social competences in the field of dealing with personal situations and the men had a higher level of social competences in situations requiring assertiveness. The women had a higher rate of emotional intelligence. No differences were found in rates of the researched persons' social competences and emotional intelligence regarding the level of studies. It was found that the respondents had a higher rate of social competences and the same rate of emotional intelligence in comparison with the results of the standardizing research.

Conclusions

- 1. Significant differences exist between the women and the men researched in the field of abilities for building social relationships. The women are more inclined to base those relations on intimacy and the men – on assertiveness.*
- 2. There is a need to stimulate the development of PE teachers' social competences and emotional intelligence during the stage of university studies and after starting professional activity. Natural social training in the work environment and standard activities during studies seem insufficient for development of these kinds of predispositions.*

Key words: *social competences, emotional intelligence, PE teacher*

Introduction

The physical education curriculum determined by provisions of the 2008 core curriculum, makes a PE teacher face a number of challenges. The most ambitious of them include realisation of the programme of health education and performing the function of its leader at school. Efficient realization of those tasks require a PE teacher to have a wide range of competences with social competences occupying the central position among them.

We understand social competences as “gained skills determining efficiency of

functioning in social situations (...) skills of dealing with other people – of understanding them, of foreseeing their behaviours correctly, of influencing them, cooperating with them and leading them [7].” To put it simply, it can be assumed that social competences mean “(...) having skills which are necessary for exertion of a desirable influence on other people in social situations” [1]. In literature there are many conceptions of social competences, some authors include abilities – usually social and emotional intelligence [16], as well social knowledge [13] – among them. Others understand social competences as both

instrumental and motivational predispositions [3]. According to the opinion of the authors of the presented paper, the behavioural aspect is that which plays the main role in dealing with social situations – what means that it reflects the essence of social competences. Cognitive, emotional and motivational predispositions are abilities which constitute the foundation for development of skills – and that is why we connect social competences with particular skills in our considerations. Those skills are: dealing with one's tasks in situations of social exposition, in intimate situations, in situations requiring assertiveness and in communication situations. Regarding the last of these, we analyse: giving orders, answering questions, praising, informing about advantages, informing about principles. It should be emphasised that according to the discussed interpretation social competences do not have a hierarchical structure. It means that none of the component skills can determine the success in a complex social situation alone. Only a specific system of them ensures efficiency of activity [1].

Emotional intelligence (EI) is defined in various ways. The most popular of these include the ability model by Mayer, Salovey and Carus, and mixed models which were developed by *inter alia*. Goleman and Bar-On. The last assumes a definitely broader perspective – for example, in Goleman's conception EI is understood as those positive human traits which do not belong to general intelligence [17].

We based our research on the ability model. According to that conception, EI is composed of: skills to perceive and express emotions; a skill to support thinking emotionally; a skill to understand and analyse emotions, a skill to use emotional knowledge and ability to control and regulate emotions in order to support emotional and intellectual development [12].

The basis of EI is conscious regulation of emotions – managing them. A person of high emotional intelligence is characterized by openness to emotions – one's own and those expressed by other people – regardless of how pleasant or unpleasant they are, s/he can recognize and interpret them, and use the results of those activities for evaluation of information or usefulness [17]. In spite of the agent attitude, the

analysis of results of the piece of research where the MEIS test (the tool which operationalized the discussed model) was used revealed the existence of the general factor of emotional intelligence [10], which justifies using a total rate while measuring EI.

In order to measure emotional intelligence self-descriptive tools or tests of abilities are used. The vulnerability of the first to conscious or unconscious distortions is recognized to be their main disadvantage. The second group are tests of abilities which also have their flaws. They are mainly accused of selection of criteria for evaluation of tasks which they include [17]. In the undertaken research the INTE test was used belonging to self-descriptive tools.

The field of human EI has been studied to a small degree. The basic questions which remain to be answered concern determining what it is (a competence, an ability or a skill), whether it changes during human lifetime and – if it does – how it changes (qualitatively or quantitatively), what connections it has with other personality constructs and skills. In our considerations we dare to formulate the thesis that it is possible to develop EI under the influence of human social experiences – including those from the field of education [11]. Moreover, we recognize it as a predictor of competences – mainly of social ones [6].

Studies of social competences and emotional intelligence of future PE teachers (university students) are rare. That is why it was decided to refer to research in that field concerning other social groups.

An interesting diagnosis of the variables we are interested in, using the same tools which are used in our study, was made by the aforementioned Martowska [6]. The author studied secondary school students aged 16-18 ($M=17.18$) – 300 persons – and adults aged 25-40 ($M=28.78$) with higher education – 232 persons. The aim of the study included, among others, researching connection between the level of social competences and emotional intelligence, on the one hand, and the course of natural social training taking place in the educational period of the researched persons' life, on the other hand.

It is interesting that the author applied the INTE test as a tool for measuring emotional competences, and not emotional intelligence, arguing that the test tasks concern evaluation of skills – and not of abilities – what seems to be an interesting and simultaneously a controversial attitude.

The analysis of results proved that there is a positive connection between the style of education by parents and social competences of the researched – the persons whose both parents applied the democratic style are characterized by the highest level of social competences. Emotional intelligence (alongside the democratic style and personal features such as temperamental activity, extrovertism and openness for experience) is a predictor of social competences. The author also suggests that emotional reactivity and neuroticism may limit and/or impede development of social competences. It was also found that the women had a higher level of competences determining dealing with intimate situations than the men – and the men had a higher level of assertiveness than the women. No differences between sexes in the field of the general level of social competences, nor in the field of competences which are necessary in the situation of social exposition were revealed. Nor were there found differences between youngsters' and adults' social competences.

M. Hen & M Goroshit researched 1st-4th year students of bachelor studies, with the social work specialisation – future health service workers dealing with mental health. A total number of 165 persons (84% of men and 16% of women) were researched. The aim of the study was to establish the influence of the special course “Being a Therapist” on the level of emotional intelligence and empathy. To measure EI the Shutte Self Report Emotional Intelligence Test was applied (its Polish version is the INTE), and – in order to diagnose the empathy level – the Interpersonal Reactivity Index. The research was carried out twice – before and after the course. The analysis of the results revealed an increase in emotional intelligence rates in the case of higher year (2nd-4th) students, whereas in the case of the 1st year students the rates had not changed. The authors also found a

small correlation between the researched persons' empathy and emotional intelligence [4]. The observed changes under the influence of the training are different depending on the researched persons' level of studies and are difficult to explain.

In the study by Otrębski and Rutkowska social competences were diagnosed and emotional intelligence of 56 professionally active sports instructors aged 21-55 (31.5 on average). The same tools as in our work were applied: the SCQ and the INTE. The authors observed that the men had a significantly higher level of social competences in dealing with situations requiring assertiveness. In the field of emotional intelligence overrepresentation of high results was observed – in relation to the normalisation research – and a small positive correlation between the rate of professional satisfaction, on the one hand, and emotional intelligence and competence of dealing with situations requiring assertiveness, on the other. The authors report a need for training sports instructors in the field of social skills. They simultaneously expect that that training can be greatly beneficial regarding revealed rates of emotional intelligence in a big proportion of the researched (21.5%) [14].

The conception of our study stems from the aforesaid theoretical and empirical perspective. We researched future PE teachers – current university students. Their future work requires first of all realisation of the didactic and educational process in conditions permitting dialogue, freedom of choice and responsibility of all subjects – pupils, their parents and teachers.

The aim of the study was to establish the level of emotional intelligence and social competences of future PE teachers. The following questions were posed:

1. What is the level of the researched students' social competences?
2. What is the level of the researched persons' emotional intelligence?
3. Does sex and the level of studies differentiate rates of the researched students' social competences and emotional intelligence?

Method

The subject of the survey were future PE teachers' social competences and emotional intelligence. Two tools were applied: the INTE questionnaire and the SCQ questionnaire.

The skills constituting emotional intelligence were studied with the INTE questionnaire by Nicola S. Schutte et al in a Polish adaptation by Anna Ciechanowicz, Aleksandra Jaworowska and Anna Matczak [8]. The tool consists of 33 items which have the character of statements. A researched person was to evaluate on a scale from 1 to 5 to what degree they refer to him/her. The internal consistency of the questionnaire is satisfying. Results of factor analyses, which prove a partial correspondence of the questionnaire with the model by Salvey and Mayer, confirm the construct validity of the tool. The questionnaire was normalized for three populations: secondary school students, tertiary school students and adults aged 21-54 [9].

The SCQ is a self-descriptive tool. Its particular items are descriptions of activities. A researched person's task is to evaluate the efficiency s/he could do them with. The tool consists of three factor scales: "I" – competences determining effectiveness of behaviours in intimate situations, "SE" – competences determining effectiveness of behaviours in situations of social expositions, "A" – competences determining effectiveness in situations requiring assertiveness. Results of the study are also presented in the form of the all-in result.

The tool is reliable and valid, which is pointed out by coefficients of internal consistency of particular scales and absolute stability. It has worked out norms for secondary school students, university students and adults [8].

The distribution of the results obtained thanks to the SCQ and the INTE was analysed by the Shapiro-Wilk test. Grouping variables were taken into account: sex and the level of studies. From the results of the test that the hypothesis about abnormality of distribution should be rejected in the case of all the analysed sets except that of the subscale SCQ-I (K: $Z(70)=0.952$; $p=0.009$) and the subscale SCQ-SE (K: $Z(70)=0.956$; $p=0.016$). For the SCQ-SE the ratio of skewness to its standard error is smaller than 2 and acceptable. For the SCQ-Int. That ratio amounts to about 2.5. Hence the distribution of those variables is different from normal, they were transformed with R function = $(61-X)^{3/4}$. Significance of difference was checked with variance analysis.

The researched were the 1st (bachelor studies) and the 2nd (master studies) level students of the Department of Physical Education at the University of Physical Education in Warsaw. After rejection of incomplete questionnaires 71 interviews remained with the 1st level students (3rd year) and 85 interviews with the 2nd level students (1st year). The age of the researched was from 20 to 26 – 22.21 on average. The whole researched group consisted of 156 students – 70 women and 86 men.

It should be emphasised that the researched students' pedagogical experience includes, among others, apprenticeships. These take place in a primary school (90 hours), a junior secondary school (90 hours) and a senior secondary school (50 hours). Apprenticeships in the last place are participated by students of master studies only. The study was made directly after the end of apprenticeships for the 1st and the 2nd level students – in a primary school and a junior secondary school in the first case and in a senior secondary school in the second.

Table 1. The researched in terms of their sex, year and level of studies

Year and level of studies ¹	Examined	N	%	Together
3 rd year of bachelor studies N = 85	Women	35	41,18	156
	Men	50	58,82	
1 st year of master studies N = 71	Women	35	49,30	
	Men	36	50,70	

¹ The chi-squared test did not revealed significant differences in numerical amount of groups which had been constructed regarding their members' sex and level of studies.

The study was made during academic classes. The respondents had been informed about the aim of the study, its anonymity and voluntary character, as well as about the way its results were going to be used. Firstly, each researched person was given the INTE questionnaire and then – after it had been filled in – the SCQ questionnaire. Each time the respondents were asked to make themselves acquainted with the instruction included in the tool.

Results of the study

Social competences come into being as a result of social training and it is justified to suppose that they grow together with gained experience. The authors decided to check whether there is a difference between the 1st level students and the master studies students regarding the level of social competences.

In literature on the subject data also exist which suggest that there are differences between sexes. Nevertheless, results of the normalization [9] were not convincing regarding that issue – the aforementioned differences were small and they appeared in an inconsistent way – and when they appeared, they were present mainly in two scales: the scale of competences determining effective functioning in intimate situations (favouring women) and the scale of competences determining effectiveness in situations requiring assertiveness (favouring men).

The variance analysis which was made did not prove the presence of statistically significant interaction effects (sex x level of studies). Hence, during further research the men's and women's results – as well as results of the students of bachelor studies and master studies – were analysed separately.

Table 2. Rates of social competences of the bachelor studies students and the master studies students

Rates	Bachelor		Master		ANOVA	
	M	SD	M	SD	F (1.152)	p
SCQ – I	46.56	5.90	45.24	7.28	1.952	0.1644
SCQ – SE	54.36	9.04	52.83	9.58	0.459	0.5009
SCQ – A	50.71	7.47	50.20	7.96	0.248	0.6192
SCQ	183.79	22.16	180.44	25.31	0.715	0.3992

A variance analysis did not reveal any statistically significant differences between rates of social competences of the students of bachelor studies and the students of master

studies. It is permitted to assume that the level of studies does not differentiate the respondents' social competences.

Table 3. The women's and the men's rates of social competences

Rates	Women		Men		ANOVA	
	M	SD	M	SD	F (1.152)	p
SCQ – I	47.59	6.99	44.63	5.93	9.492	0.0025 ¹
SCQ – SE	54.83	9.19	52.72	9.33	0.1850	0.6686
SCQ – A	49.36	7.87	51.80	6.98	3.585	0.0602 ²
SCQ	184.11	24.01	180.76	23.33	1.095	0.2970

¹ Differences are significant on the level $p < 0,05$

² Differences are significant on the tendency level $p < 0.1$

An analysis of rates of the women's and the men's general social competences did not prove significant differences between them. Regarding the distinguished subscales, it was observed that the women had significantly higher rates of competences in dealing with intimate situations,

whereas the men had higher rates of competences in dealing with situations which require assertiveness. In the case of dealing with situations of social expositions no significant differences were found.

Print 1. Distribution of the women's competences in managing intimate situations (SCQ-I.)

The distribution of rates of the women's competences in managing intimate situations deserves attention (Print 1). As it has already been mentioned, it is skewed. (Shapiro-Wilk test

$= -0.765$). It means that in the researched group there is overrepresentation of the female students with higher rates of those competences.

Print. 2. Distribution of rates of of the men's competences in dealing with intimate situations (SCQ-I.)

In the case of the men the distribution of results is normal (Shapiro-Wilk test = - 0.012).

Table 4. Rates of emotional intelligence of the researched women and men

Rate	Women		Men		ANOVA	
	M	SD	M	SD	F (1,152)	p
INTE	132.43	11,86	127.58	14.43	5.58	0.0195 ¹

¹ Difference is significant for $p < 0.05$

An analysis of variances reveals significantly higher rates of emotional intelligence in the case of the women. The value of

dispersion points to greater differentiation of the obtained rates in the case of the men.

Table 5. Rate of emotional intelligence of the students of master and bachelor studies

Rate	Bachelor		Master		ANOVA	
	M	SD	M	SD	F (1,152)	p
INTE	130.07	13,35	129,38	13,80	0.17	0.6849

No significant differences regarding rates of emotional intelligence between the bachelor studies students and the master studies students were found.

In order to evaluate the level of the diagnosed social competences and emotional intelligence we referred the obtained results to the raw data and to the sten norms obtained from the normalization research, where it had

been assumed that results ranging from the 1st to the 3rd sten correspond to a low level of social competences, the 4th, 5th, 6th and the 7th sten mean an average level, whereas results ranging from the 8th till 10th sten mean a high level [5, 9].

Analysis reveals that 12.81% of the researched students have low social competences. The percentages of men and

women are the same. 54.9% of those researched have average social competences. They are had by a significantly higher rate of the men (63.96%) than of the women (40.86%). Students with the highest social competences constitute 32.96%. The percentage of the women belonging to that group is higher (44.28%) than that of the men (23.3%).

Comparison of average rates of general social competences obtained in the normalization research on a group of students of various specialisations (women $M=170.82$; $SD=21.09$; men $M=176.28$; $SD=22.38$) revealed that they are significantly lower than those obtained in our study (women: $M=184.11$; $SD=24.01$; men: $M=180.76$; $SD=23.33$) [9]. It should be mentioned that the normalization research did not consider students of physical education departments and students of pedagogical specialisations were researched instead of them.

In the case of emotional intelligence its low level was ascertained in 12.18% of those researched. Differences between the women and the men are insignificant. The average level of emotional intelligence is manifested by 55.13% of the respondents. In the group of men such persons constitute 51.16% and in the group of the women – 59.98. High emotional intelligence was diagnosed in 32.96% of the researched – 30% of the women and 34.88% of the men.

Mean results of the normalization research on a group of students ($M = 127.91$; $SD = 13.47$) are not significantly different from those obtained in our research ($M= 129.76$, $SD=13.56$) [5].

Discussion

The paper was aimed at diagnosing emotional intelligence and social competences of future PE teachers – students of the Department of Physical education at the University of Physical Education in Warsaw.

The obtained rates of emotional intelligence prove that its level is average. Comparing them with results of the normalization research [9] and results of studies by other authors [14, 4, 6] we find that their values are not significantly different.

In our study, similarly to the works of the aforementioned authors, there were not observed any differences of emotional intelligence or social competences regarding the respondents' age, level of studies and pedagogical experience. In the case of the experimental studies which are mentioned in the paper, differences which occurred in the field of emotional intelligence under the influence of the introduced educational program (which was rather extensive) appeared only in one group of students [4]. This is quite difficult to explain. We can only speculate that the discussed dispositions – and especially emotional intelligence – develop under the influence of social training at an earlier period of life and that is the source of individual differences which later are only maintained. It seems also possible that lack of differences between researched persons of different ages and experience results from the fact that natural social training, which is an element of their life, at some stage of life is no more effective regarding further development of emotional intelligence and social competences. It is also possible to recognize the intervention of interfering variables, which appear with age. This is pointed out by Matczak when he explains finding higher rates of SC in youngsters than in adults: adults may be more critical in their self-evaluation. [9].

The observed differences favouring the women in the field of emotional intelligence are revealed also by other studies [6, 14]. Women's supremacy can be explained by both sexes' different courses of development. Girls markedly earlier than boys develop verbal communication skills. They also begin the stage of adolescence earlier and take on various social roles [15]. It is possible that their high (usually higher than in the case of boys) development activity in early years of life stimulates development of emotional intelligence, whose higher level manifests itself at later stages.

In the case of rates of general social competences, we have ascertained that those obtained in our research were significantly higher than those in the normalization research. It is possible that it results from PE students' specific experiences. Educational milieus coming into being in the area of physical culture (a sports

club, an exercising group) generate situations of intense interactions. They can be outstandingly stimulating for development of social competences of participants of activities.

Our research has revealed differences between the women and the men in the field of dealing with intimate situations (women were better) and in situations requiring assertiveness (men were better). Differences were not observed in the case of dealing with situations of social exposition. In the quoted studies, as well as in the normalization research, similar dependencies were observed – although of different intensity. Those differences can be explained by different characteristics of women's and men's social role – where intimacy and protectiveness still seem to dominate in the case of women while independence and firmness are clearly emphasised in the case of men [2]. In spite of the fact that sex in our research does not differentiate rates of the women's and the men's general social competences, different courses of social interactions during professional activities of female teachers and male teachers should be expected. The first are probably going to perform better in relations based on emotional closeness (with pupils and parents) and to be better in the realization of education tasks connected with stimulation of development of those competences in pupils. The men are probably going to be more efficient in situations requiring assertiveness.

In the case of making attempts at shaping social competences – during studies or after beginning professional activity – it seems reasonable to organize coeducational groups aimed at the common work of their participants

and providing them with proper space for exchange and modelling of behaviours.

According to the conceptions of social competences and emotional intelligence which have been presented in the paper they may be recognized as key elements of a PE teacher's professional profile. Their proper development gives a chance for efficiency at work and a successful private life. Hence it seems justified to pose the question: how should development of PE teachers' social competences and emotional intelligence be stimulated?

Conclusions

1. The researched persons' level of emotional intelligence and social competences promise their success in their future work as educators in the field of physical culture and health culture.
2. There are significant differences between the researched women and the researched men concerning their ability to build social relationships. The women are more inclined to base those relationships on intimacy and the men – on assertiveness.
3. There is a need for stimulation of development of PE teachers' social competences and emotional intelligence at the stage of studies and after undertaking professional activities. Natural social training in a work environment, as well as standard classes during studies, seem insufficient for development of those dispositions. Trainings should be based on participants' experience and modelling of behaviours.

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Correspondence

Marcin Czechowski

University of Physical Education in Warsaw,
Address: ul. Marymoncka 34, 00-968 Warszawa
E-mail: marcin.czechowski@awf.edu.pl